

Personal and systemic responsibility for developing resilience in research workplaces

Cahill Brian¹, Solymosi Katalin², Lewandowska Aleksandra³, Kismihók Gábor⁴, Metcalfe Janet⁵, Björnmalm Mattias⁶

¹ Learning and Skills Analytics / Governing Board, Leibniz Information Centre for Science and Technology / EuroScience, Germany

² Eötvös Loránd University / Young Academy of Europe, Hungary

³ Board Member | Research Assistant and Ombudsperson for Doctoral Candidates Rights, EURODOC | Uniwersytet w Białymstoku, Poland

⁴ Leibniz Information Centre for Science and Technology, Germany

⁵ Vitae, United Kingdom

⁶ General Secretary, CESAER, Belgium

Recent studies have indicated a higher likelihood of early-career researchers developing mental illnesses compared to their peers. Completion rates of PhD programs in many European countries are notably low. The ReMO COST Action has increased awareness of mental health issues within academia, evaluated the evidence base for best practices, and successfully advocated for the inclusion of mental health in the recently approved European Charter for Researchers. The Human Resources Strategy for Researchers (HRS4R) will now incorporate mental health services into the accreditation process necessary for obtaining EU research funding. This session will examine which best practices can serve as a model for research institutions in Europe. Addressing researcher mental health often involves a stronger emphasis on personal responsibility and training to assist individuals in addressing personal development issues and adopting professional work practices. While these efforts are valuable, it is insufficient to solely rely on individuals to develop the resilience needed to cope with and overcome systematic threats to their mental well-being. There is a clear need for research institutions, research funders, and policymakers to assess their ability to facilitate systemic change in our research workplaces. This may include ensuring sustainable academic career paths, reforming research assessment processes, implementing best practice guidelines (such as those pertaining to supervision, bullying, research integrity, and whistleblowing), reducing the stigma surrounding mental health, and enhancing levels of professional supervision within the research environment. This session will explore how we can ensure that doctoral education provides greater value for all stakeholders.

Form of presentation
Debate (min. 3 speakers)

Keywords
mental health, mental wellbeing, resilience, supervision, research careers, doctoral education, best practices, academia

Bibliography
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Additional information

Information about speakers
Number of speakers: 5 speakers